

Parents' Perception of Factors Responsible for Inaccessibility of Children with Disabilities to Basic Education in Rural Areas of Niger State

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Abstract

This study investigated parents' perceptions of the factors contributing to the inaccessibility of basic education for children with disabilities in rural areas of Niger State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design, the research focused on a purposively selected sample of 150 parents of children with disabilities. Data were collected through a validated self-developed questionnaire titled Education Accessibility Factors Questionnaire, with reliability confirmed through the split-half method, yielding a coefficient of 0.87. Of the 120 distributed questionnaires, 112 were adequately completed and analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The findings revealed four primary factors hindering access to basic education for children with disabilities namely; social perception, poverty, parental attitude and lack of physical facilities and resources. The study found no significant differences in perceptions based on the gender of parents. However, differences were observed based on the type of disability, with parents of children with varying disabilities highlighting unique challenges and needs. To address these barriers, the study recommends leveraging digital pedagogy to reduce educational costs, establishing inclusive and well-equipped schools, and creating disability-friendly school environments. These interventions aim to ensure equitable access to education for children with disabilities, fostering inclusion and empowerment in rural communities.

Key words: basic education, disability, parents, inaccessibility

Introduction

Education is an indispensable right of every child irrespective of his/her peculiarity. The purpose of education is to assist an individual to achieve cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills to develop attitude, aptitude and behaviour than can enhance positive and healthy living. Basic education is a nine (9) year programme provided are the primary and lower secondary school. This type of education is given to children ranges from 0 to 15 years of age (Federal Government of Nigeria – FGN; 2013). Basic education is designed with the purpose of providing children basic skills for entrepreneurship, wealth generation and educational advancement. Basic education as a foundation is linked to many benefits ranging from personal gain through immediate family advantage to national benefits at large.

Disappointingly, not all children especially children living with disabilities enjoy their right to basic education. Disability is any condition of the body or mind that makes it more difficult for the children with the condition to function appropriately and actively interacts with the environment. As reviewed by Bianquin and Bulgarelli (2016), disability is considered as the consequence or the product of a compound association among individual's health condition, personal factors and environment that represent the situations in which the individual lives.

The concept disability has been debated; medical and social models have been adopted in debating the concept. Gutterman (2023) looked at disability using four diverse models; moral model considering the repercussion of sin, medical model seeing disability as defect, rehabilitation model viewing disability as deficiency that must be fixed and disability model which considers the problem as dominating attitude and sensory, cognitive and economic obstacles. Rohwerder (2015) in Gutterman (2023) considered five models which are: charity, medical, social, human right and interactional models.

In 2018 about 29 million of the 195 million people in Nigeria were living with a disability (World Bank, 2020). The number of children with disabilities globally was estimated at about 240 million (UNICEF report, 2021). In Nigeria, about 25 million people have one form of disability or the other, accounting for 15% of the population (Akeem and Usman (2023). According to UNICEF, about 95% of children with disabilities in developing countries are out of school. In Niger State, according to statistic from Ministry of Education, Minna only 2051 children living with disabilities are enrolled in basic education level. The right of children with disabilities to education is acknowledged explicitly by constitutions, laws and policies around the world. Article 24 of the United Nations convention on the rights of persons with disabilities (UNCRPD), which has been ratified by 185 countries, recognises the rights of children with disabilities to access education without discrimination (United Nation, 2006). In spite of these laws and policies, children with disabilities have difficulties in gaining access to basic education. Some factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities include parent's attitude to the education of children with disabilities, physical facilities and resources, social perception

and poverty. Young men and women, face attitudinal, physical, institutional, financial and communication barriers in accessing basic services, including education (Kyari & Adekoya, 2024).

Aruldas et al. (2023) explores the factors affecting children with disabilities' enrolment and experience in school in Tamil Nadu, India. 40 caregivers and 20 children with disabilities were purposively selected and interviewed. Overall, caregivers recognised the essence of school for their children's future livelihoods or at least as a means of socialisation. However, some questioned the value of school, particularly for children with intellectual or sensory impairments. The finding show that poor availability and affordability of transport, safety concerns or school staffs' concerns about children's behaviour being disruptive, lack of teacher training and resources for inclusive education, poor physical accessibility of schools, as well as negative or overly protective attitudes from teachers and peers are barriers to school enrolment and regular attendance.

In the study of Adjanku (2020) on Barriers to access and enrolment for children with disabilities in pilot inclusive schools in Bole District in Ghana. Using random sampling and purposive sampling technique, ten schools practicing the inclusive education whose teachers were the target for the study were selected. The results revealed that majority of the respondents agreed teachers show negative attitudes towards children with special needs, schools environments are physically not accessible to children with disabilities and teachers are not trained towards teaching children with disabilities.

According to Mont (2019), there are strong relationships between lack of access to education and poverty for children with disabilities. He reported that many studies have understated the relationships that exist between disability and poverty because they do not take into account the additional costs of living with a disability. For a given level of income, a household with a disabled family member is less well off than households without a disabled member because they have additional expenses related to health care, transportation, assistive devices, personal assistance, housing needs, etc. Against this background, the study therefore surveyed the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by their parent and caregivers.

Statement of the problem

Education is for all, children living with disabilities inclusive. Inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education is a denial of fundamental human right. This remains the crucial risk factor in Nigeria for problems of high poverty rate, street begging, kidnapping, increase welfare costs, future dependence, unemployment, decrease productivity and wealth creation. For effective intervention, there is need to identify the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education, thereby providing measures in addressing the problem.

Objectives of the Study

The study is to determine the:

1. Factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by their parents.
2. Difference in perception of parent on the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education base in gender and child disability type.

Research questions

1. What are the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by their parents?
2. What is the difference in perception of parent on the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education base in gender and child disability type?

Hypotheses

Ho1. There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on gender.

Ho2. There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on child disability type.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The choice of descriptive survey is that it helps to obtain pertinent and precise information concerning the present status or condition of a phenomenon under investigation. The population for the study comprised parents of children living with disabilities in Niger State, Nigeria. The researchers purposively sampled one hundred and fifty parents of children living with disability Niger States, Nigeria.

A self-developed questionnaire titled 'Education Accessibility Factors' Questionnaire was validated to obtain information for the study from the respondents. To measure contents validity of the instruments, it was given to three experts in the field of Psychology, Special Education and Measurement. The corrections, observations, suggestions and comments made by the experts were effected which adjudged the instruments to be valid for this study. Using split half method of reliability, the measures of stability of the instruments was established and 0.87 coefficient obtained was considered adequate for the study. 120 questionnaires were administered to respondents; 112 adequately filled questionnaires were scored, coded and analysed for the study using descriptive statistics of means and standard deviation and inferential statistics of Mann Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Walis test.

Result Presentation

Research Questions One: What are the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by their parents?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores of factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education

SN	Item	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Educating my disabled child is a waste of resource	112	3.30	0.89	Agree
2	it is not obligatory to send disabled children to school	112	3.32	0.71	Agree
3	I feel ashamed when my disabled child is publically seen	112	3.32	0.82	Agree
4	I feel better when my disabled child is with me because I fear no one will care for him/her.	112	3.19	0.62	Agree
5	I'm afraid something might happen such as accident when the attend school	112	3.25	0.83	Agree
6	Schools for person with disabilities are too far from their residence	112	3.50	0.73	Agree
7	No specialized teachers especially in inclusive schools	112	3.15	0.79	Agree
8	Inadequate of specialized equipment and facilities for the education of persons with disabilities	112	3.26	0.69	Agree
9	Available schools do not have ramps and/or elevators in buildings to cater for children with disabilities	112	3.08	1.03	Agree
10	No adequate and affordable transport system	112	3.26	.995	Agree
11	Teachers and students Discrimination against children with disabilities	112	3.49	.771	Agree
12	Stigmatization; people call them names	112	3.35	.655	Agree
13	Teachers feel everything need to be done for children with disabilities	112	3.35	.745	Agree
14	Social sympathy toward persons with disabilities	112	3.18	.811	Agree
15	Cultural belief that person with disability is a curse, tragedy and an object for ritual	112	3.37	.784	Agree
16	I couldn't afford sending him to school	112	3.45	.642	Agree
17	I need money to get the school uniform cleaned on daily basis	112	3.27	.725	Agree
18	He/she is an additional expenditure on the family	112	3.00	.900	Agree
19	I couldn't afford to transport him to and from every day	112	3.22	.936	Agree
20	Materials needed for effective study are expensive	112	3.58	.778	Agree
Grand mean		112	3.29	0.34	

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by their parents. This indicates that all the items score more than 2.5 decision mean, with grand mean of 3.29 which imply that all the twenty items were accepted, an indication that the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by their parents is positive. From table 1, the factor with the highest mean is item 20 which show the expensiveness of materials needed for effective study with a mean score of 3.58. The factor with the lowest mean score is item 18 which indicate that disabled children are perceived additional expenditure on the family. Based

on the table, parents agree with all items 1 – 20 as factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education. The factor are categorised into four; Item 1 – 5 (parents' attitude), 6 - 10 (Physical Facilities/Resources). 11 - 15 (Social Perception) and 16 – 20 (poverty). A summary of the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents of disability based on the four subsections of the factors is presented thus:

Table 2: Summary of factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education and their mean Score

S/N	Factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Parent's Attitude	3.28	.774	Agree
2	Physical Facilities/Resources	3.25	.841	Agree
3	Social Perception	3.35	.753	Agree
4	Poverty	3.30	.796	Agree

Table 2 reveals that the main factor responsible for the inaccessibility of children with disabilities to education is social perception; the manner in which the people around perceived the children with disabilities. These include the social discrimination, stigmatization, weak and someone who needs sympathy. Another factor is poverty; parent couldn't afford the expenses of enrolling their disabled child in school due to the cost attached such as purchase of materials and transportation. The third factor as perceived by parents is parents' attitude which shows what the parents feel about their disabled child and education. To them educating them is a waste of resources and some are over protective, therefore scared of what will happen in their absence as parent. The least factor is physical facilities/resources involving distance of school, lack of specialized teachers, equipment and ramps in school buildings.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on gender.

Table 3: Mann-Whitney U-test on factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on gender

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	z	Sign
Male	66	59.29	3913.00	1334.000	2415.000	-1.090	0.276
Female	46	52.50	2415.00				

Table 3 shows Mann-Whitney U-test analysis on factors responsible for inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education based on gender. The table indicates that there is no significant difference in the perception of male and female parents on the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education. The table 3 show p-value = 0.276 since value of $p > 0.05$, H_{01} , therefore, hypothesis one was accepted.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on child disability type.

Table 4: Kruskal-Walis test of the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on child disability type

Child Disability	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Df	Sig
Physically challenged	34	41.41	26.072	3	0.00
Hearing Impaired	18	86.58			
Blind	26	64.56			
Others	34	49.50			

Table 4 shows the hypothesis that stated that no significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on child disability type was tested. The findings of the table show $df = 3$, with $p = 0.00$ Since $p < 0.05$, H_{02} , was rejected. Therefore there was significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on child disability type.

Discussion of Finding

The result of the study showed the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education in Niger State. The first factor as revealed in the study was social perception; the manner in which the people around perceived the children with disabilities. These individuals include teachers, neighbours, friends and peers. The children living with disabilities are discriminated against, stigmatized, considered as weak and someone who needs sympathy. According to Limaye (2016) parent's attitude toward their disabled child and education is a key factor responsible for their education. He observed that the social stigma experienced by the parents is transferred to their disabled child. Some parents of disabled children queried the importance of education for children with disabilities, when there is no job for them.

Another factor is poverty; parents couldn't afford the expenses of enrolling their disabled children in school due to the cost attached such as purchase of materials and transportation. This is supported by the study of Mont (2019) that found a strong relationship between lack of access to education and poverty for children with disabilities. He explained that a household with a disabled family member is less well off than households

without a disabled member due to extra costs related to health care, transportation, assistive devices, personal assistance and housing needs.

The third factor as perceived by parents is parents' attitude which shows what the parents feel about their disabled child and education. To them, educating disabled children is a waste of resources and some are over protective, therefore scared of what will happen in their absence as parent.

The fourth factor is physical facilities/resources. Parents expressed that distance of school to the resident of the disabled, lack of specialized teachers, equipment and ramps in school buildings are factors that responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education. The study of Aruldas et al (2023) that explores the factors affecting children with disabilities' enrolment and experience in school found that poor availability and affordability of transport, lack of teacher training and resources for inclusive education and poor physical accessibility of schools are barriers to school enrolment and regular attendance. Limaye (2016) revealed that infrastructure, inadequate levels of training of key stakeholders such as teacher hinder accessibility to education.

The finding revealed that there is no significant difference in the perception of male and female parents on the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education. The study also revealed that there was significant difference in the factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education as perceived by parents based on child disability type. This may be as result of the peculiarity in health and need of each category of persons with disability.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that social perception, parent's attitude, poverty and physical facilities/resources are factors responsible for the inaccessibility of children with disability to basic education in Niger State. The father and mother of disabled children do not differ on these factors. However, different parents of different categories of disability such as the physically challenged, blind, hearing and impaired have differ on the factors.

Recommendations

In consonant with the research findings, the researchers recommend as follows:

1. Government should leverage digital pedagogy to increase accessibility of children living with disabilities to basic education. This will help in reducing the cost of education of person with disabilities and that of providing inclusive education for the disabilities.
2. Government should also create a functioning inclusive basic school, well equipped and accommodative to children with disabilities.

3. School authorities and teachers should make school environments more disability friendly and make other schools facilities more accessible to children with special needs.
4. Efforts should be made to launch community-based awareness campaigns to combat stigma and promote positive attitudes toward children with disabilities and their education.
5. Government should collaborate with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and private sector partners to provide financial assistance, scholarships, and resources to families of children with disabilities.

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